

Assisting the Remote Assistant: Augmenting Degraded Video Streams with Additional Sensor Data to Improve Situation Awareness in Complex Urban Traffic

Andreas Schrank¹ [0000-0001-8352-1052], Nils Wendorff¹ [0009-0000-0457-3912] and Michael Oehl¹ [0000-0002-0871-2286]

¹ German Aerospace Center (DLR), Institute of Transportation Systems, Lilienthalplatz 7,
38108 Braunschweig, Germany
andreas.schrank@dlr.de, nils.wendorff@dlr.de,
michael.oehl@dlr.de

Abstract. Remotely operating highly automated vehicles (HAVs, SAE 4 [1]) bears the potential to boost their large-scale deployment. A human operator supports the vehicle automation remotely in situations that exceed the automation's capabilities. A high-quality video stream displaying the HAV's environment is key for the remote operator to obtain and maintain situation awareness. One of the major technical obstacles is the frequent and serious limitation of connectivity between the remote operator and the HAV, particularly a drop of bandwidth. This results in a severely degraded video resolution. As a remedy, we propose the use of data transmitted from the HAV's additional onboard sensors to augment a low-resolution video stream. A significantly lower bandwidth suffices to transmit sensor data compared to video data, enabling their transmission even when the video resolution is degraded. This could help the remote operator gain situation awareness, particularly in remote assistance, a variant of remote operation in which the operator provides high-level advice to the vehicle [2]. To confirm the need for a sensor data augmented view of the traffic situation, an experimental online user study ($N = 117$) was conducted. The study presented short video clips of complex naturalistic urban road traffic to participants. The objective was to examine if overlaying the video stream with visualized sensor data improves a remote assistant's situation awareness and whether the effect of overlaid sensor data depends on the video resolution. Results revealed a significant effect of video resolution on objective situation awareness. Additionally, an interaction effect between resolution and sensor-data overlay became evident on the perception level of situation awareness. Hence, sensor data augmentation of degraded video streams may support the remote assistant's situation awareness by increasing the salience of relevant elements in a traffic situation. Future research will investigate sensor data augmentation in a standardized simulation environment.

Keywords: Remote operation, remote assistance, human-machine interaction, highly automated vehicles

1 Introduction

Remote operation is a gateway to highly automated and connected driving. New legal regulations both on national and EU level make remote operation a prerequisite for the deployment of highly automated vehicles (HAV, SAE 4 [1]) on public roads. As stated in the 2021 German Road Traffic Act [3], a “technical supervisor” is required to oversee automated driving operations and intervene if necessary. In its remote implementation, the technical supervisor’s role overlaps with SAE’s [1] definition of a “remote assistant” (RA), a specific variant of a remote operator. Given the legal constraints, it is strongly assumed remote assistance is currently the only legally permissible implementation of remote operation, at least in Germany.

Kettwich et al. [4] proposed a human-machine interface (HMI) for the RA’s workplace in line with these legal requirements and proved it to be effective and user-friendly. Schrank et al. [5] showed that this workplace HMI is viable even under increased levels of induced cognitive load. In addition to performance, these studies confirmed that establishing and maintaining situation awareness (SA) is key for safe and effective remote assistance (see also [6]). A valid representation of the traffic environment around the supervised HAV that enables the RA to perceive the relevant elements in the situation precisely (SA level 1 [7]) needs to be conveyed to the RA. Only if the perception of all relevant elements is ensured, a valid wholistic representation of the situation may emerge (SA level 2) which allows an accurate prediction of how the situation will unfold (SA level 3). Thus, it is pivotal for the remote assistance of HAVs to ensure the RA has sufficient SA. [4]’s HMI mainly relies on the video stream transmitted from the HAV to the RA. This is common for remote operation HMIs in general [8]. However, in real-world operations, connectivity restraints in mobile networks such as low bandwidth may degrade the quality of the video stream, e.g., by lowering its resolution. This can be detrimental for the RA’s SA as the perception of relevant elements may be impaired, deteriorating SA overall.

In order to maintain a sufficient degree of SA even in the event of poor connectivity, strategies to compensate for these restraints are needed. We suggest that additional sensor data, e.g., from Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) or radar sensors, be visualized to augment the video stream. This comes with at least three advantages: First, sensor data serve as an additional source of information that may shed light on objects in an environment that the RA might not have detected otherwise, increasing the RA’s SA. For instance, this could be the case in unfavorable light or weather conditions. Second, the bandwidth required to transmit sensor data is considerably lower than for transmitting high-resolution video streams. Even when network performance is poor, sensor data may still be transmissible when high-resolution video streams are not. Third, sensor data from HAVs are readily available. Since the HAV’s perception of the environment relies on sensor data, sensors that produce visualizable output are often part of an HAV’s standard hardware equipment. Alternatively, sensor data originating from infrastructure, e.g., from road-site units, could be utilized.

For the effective and efficient use of sensor data in remote assistance, however, a user-centered visualization of the sensor data and their interplay with the video stream data is pivotal. This visualization could be the cornerstone of a novel HMI for remote

assistance. Figure 1 presents an exemplary visualization of LiDAR data as an overlay of the video stream to aid the RA's SA.

Fig. 1. Example for visualization of sensor data from real traffic environment. Data from vehicle's LiDAR sensor are laid over video stream with low resolution as a point cloud. Algorithms were applied to classify the LiDAR points in the traffic environment. Relevant object classes are color-coded as follows: vehicles in blue and vulnerable road users (pedestrians and cyclists) in yellow, for example.

To ascertain if the augmented view helps users obtain SA, an online user study was conducted. In addition to the question whether augmenting the video stream with visualized sensor data improves SA in general, it is conceivable that such an augmentation might affect SA particularly positively when the resolution of the video stream is lower, e.g., due to connectivity issues. It is argued that by overlaying a degraded video stream with visualized sensor data, a compensatory effect may become evident: Remote assistants may be able to obtain the required visual information from the sensor data in lieu of the video stream, compensating for the lack of higher resolution.

Previous research has indeed shown that lower video stream quality impedes the remote operator's SA [9]. However, the study focused on remote driving and did not specify what specific driving scenarios were used. To the authors' knowledge, whether a degraded video stream of real driving scenarios negatively affects SA in remote assistance has not yet been investigated in the literature. Additionally, no research for remote assistance on the effects of an interplay between an augmented video stream and different video resolutions could be found in the literature.

Therefore, this paper aims to evaluate the effect of augmenting the video stream that is displayed to the remote assistant's workplace with visualized sensor data on situation awareness. Stimuli are complex urban situations recorded in real-world traffic that are relevant for remote assistance. As it is hypothesized that augmenting the video stream is particularly beneficial for situation awareness in situations with lower resolution, i.e.,

when the video stream is degraded, the resolution of the video stream will be systematically varied.

2 Methods

2.1 Participants and Experimental Design

117 participants (39 female, $M_{\text{age}} = 36.19$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 15.40$, 18 to 82 years) completed an experimental online study. Participants had to be at least 18 years and possess a valid driver's license. The study applied a between-subject design with each participant randomly assigned to one of the four conditions of Augmentation \times Resolution (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Screenshot from the video sections (recorded at 20 Hz) of complex, urban, real traffic situation presented to participants. Note the pedestrian on the right shoulder trying to cross the street, highlighted in yellow in the Augmentation conditions. (a) High Resolution – No Augmentation condition with the recorded resolution of 2046×1024 pixel; (b) Low Resolution – No Augmentation condition with the resolution reduced to 10 percent and then re-upscaled to its original resolution without interpolation; (c) High Resolution – Augmentation condition with overlaid LiDAR point cloud as described in Fig. 1; (d) High Resolution – Augmentation condition.

2.2 Materials

The presented videos were recorded by cameras mounted onto a research vehicle [10] during test drives in real urban traffic. The video stream was searched for sections with complex and ambiguous traffic situations that may require the intervention of a RA. Each section was ten seconds long. Seven sections were selected, one of which was used for training purposes. Depending on condition, resolution and/or augmentation were adjusted (Fig. 2).

2.3 Measures

To measure situation awareness (SA) objectively, a query-based questionnaire was created, inspired by the Situation Awareness Global Assessment Technique (SAGAT) [11]. In SAGAT, a situation is “frozen” and questions about it are asked, which are then used to measure three levels of SA as defined by [7]. Unlike in SAGAT, the video sections here stopped playing 10 seconds after onset for each video and did not resume.

Individual responses for SA levels 1 and 2 were developed for each of the six video sections, which participants had to rate as correct or incorrect. One point was awarded for each correct response, and a response was considered correct only if a true statement was checked or a wrong statement was not checked [12]. For SA level 3, responses were the same throughout all video sections. Each participant’s SA score was determined by the number of correct responses [13].

Table 1 lists questionnaire items, respective responses and the maximum number of points for each SA level. In total, participants could score 11 points for each of the six video sections. Following [7]’s theory of SA, items for level 1 queried the participant’s perception of relevant elements in the traffic environment, for level 2 the understanding of the situation, and for level 3 the projection, operationalized as the future behavior of the monitored vehicle “to reach the destination quickly and safely”.

Table 1. Items and responses of developed questionnaire to measure objective situation awareness.

SA Level	Item	Responses ¹	Maximum of Points Granted
1	What did you observe in the situation?	The road had a solid line A person was standing on the road A vehicle was blocking a lane The traffic light was yellow Pedestrians were waiting at the pedestrian light to cross the street The vehicle in front was using the direction indicator (turn signal)	6 (multiple responses may be correct; 1 point for every correctly checked or unchecked response)
2		The vehicle ahead had to change lanes at least once	4 (multiple responses may be

	What did you observe in the situation?	<p>The monitored vehicle was able to change to the right lane at any time</p> <p>The monitored vehicle could not turn right at the traffic light because a vehicle was blocking the lane</p> <p>The monitored vehicle had to pass a vehicle that was blocking a lane</p>	<p>correct; 1 point for every correctly checked or unchecked response)</p>
3	How should the monitored vehicle behave to get to its destination quickly and safely for all road users?	<p>Continue driving</p> <p>Go over a green light</p> <p>Change to the right lane</p> <p>Change to the left lane</p> <p>Turn right</p> <p>Turn left</p> <p>Overtake vehicle in front of me</p> <p>Brake and continue driving at reduced speed</p> <p>Brake and bring the vehicle to a stop</p>	1 (only one response is correct)

¹ Responses are examples only for SA levels 1 and 2 as on these levels, responses are tailored to each distinct video section. For Level 3, responses are the same across video sections.

2.4 Procedure

First, participants were informed about the general scope and objectives of the study. Second, participants indicated their demographical data including age and gender. Third, the notion of remote assistance, an exemplary workplace for remote assistance, and the task they had to complete were presented to participants. Participants were prompted to imagine to work as a remote assistant (RA). They were told that the video sections they were presented showed different traffic situations recorded by an automated vehicle. This vehicle requested assistance from them because it could not solve a certain complex urban traffic situation. Their task was to view the video section recorded ten seconds prior to the request and answer questions about the traffic situation. After viewing the video section and assisting the vehicle, it would resume the automated mode. This prompt was based on the notion that viewing a short video clip of the period before an automated vehicle's request for assistance may improve SA of remote operators [14]. Fourth, participants were randomly assigned to one of the four conditions of Augmentation \times Resolution. A test trial was run in the assigned condition. Just as the following experimental trials, it consisted of a 10-seconds video section of a traffic situation (see "Materials") and the developed SA questionnaire (see "Measures"). Each video section could be viewed only once. After each video section ended, participants had unlimited time to respond to the respective SA questionnaire. Fifth, participants ran through the six randomized experimental trials with one video section each and completed the respective questions.

3 Results

The following section reports the statistical analyses regarding objective and subjective situation awareness (SA).

In terms of objective situation awareness, descriptive results are presented in Table 2. A two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a significant effect of condition on the overall objective SA score (Table 3). The only significant factor was Resolution. Pairwise post-hoc comparisons showed that the only significant effect between conditions was between the two conditions High Resolution and Low Resolution, each without Augmentation ($M_{\text{Diff}} = 0.850$, $p = .022$).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of objective situation awareness overall.

Condition	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
High Res. – No Augm.	8.227	1.157
High Res. – Augm.	7.975	1.104
Low Res. – No Augm.	7.377	0.948
Low Res. – Augm.	7.806	1.033
Total	7.841	1.085

Res. = Resolution; Augm. = Augmentation. Range: [0;11].

Table 3. The effect of condition on the score of objective situation awareness overall in two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Condition	Sum of Squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Corrected Model	11.343	3	3.781	3.410	.020
Intercept	6964.430	1	6964.430	6281.259	.000
Augmentation	.013	1	.013	.012	.914
Resolution	9.500	1	9.500	8.568	.004
Resolution × Augmentation	2.132	1	2.132	1.922	.168
Error	125.290	113	1.109		
Total	7328.944	117			

$R^2 = .083$ (corrected $R^2 = .059$).

Table 4 presents descriptive statistics for scores of level 1 objective situation awareness. As shown in Table 5, A two-way ANOVA yielded a global significant effect of condition on the level 1 score of objective SA. However, unlike in the overall objective SA score, not only Resolution was shown to have a significant main effect on the level 1 score but also the interaction effect between Resolution and Augmentation reached significance (Table 5). Again, pairwise post-hoc comparisons showed that this effect was driven by a single significant difference between High-Resolution and Low-

Resolution conditions, each without Augmentation ($M_{\text{Diff}}=0.626$, $p = .002$). On SA levels 2 and 3, no significant differences between conditions were found.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics of objective situation awareness at level 1.

Condition	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
High Res. – No Augm.	4.626	0.625
High Res. – Augm.	4.407	0.736
Low Res. – No Augm.	4.000	0.525
Low Res. – Augm.	4.294	0.605
Total	4.356	0.658

Res. = Resolution; Augm. = Augmentation. Range: [0;6].

Table 5. The effect of condition on the score of objective situation awareness at level 1 in two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Condition	Sum of Squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Corrected Model	5.527	3	1.842	4.658	.004
Intercept	2141.140	1	2141.140	5413.919	.000
Augmentation	0.040	1	0.040	0.102	.750
Resolution	3.900	1	3.900	9.862	.002
Resolution × Augmentation	1.876	1	1.876	4.745	.031
Error	44.690	113	0.395		
Total	2270.389	117			

$R^2 = .110$ (corrected $R^2 = .086$).

Regarding subjective awareness measured by SART scores, no significant effects of condition on SART score were observed (Table 6).

Table 6. The effect of condition on the score of subjective situation awareness (SART) in two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Condition	Sum of Squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Corrected Model	9.673 ^a	3	3.224	1.366	.257
Intercept	2161.298	1	2161.298	915.721	.000
Augmentation	0.187	1	0.187	0.079	.779
Resolution	5.991	1	5.991	2.538	.114
Resolution × Augmentation	4.178	1	4.178	1.770	.186
Error	266.704	113	2.360		
Total	2528.852	117			

$R^2 = .035$ (corrected $R^2 = .009$).

4 Discussion and Outlook

This user study investigated the effect of a video stream for a remote assistant of highly automated vehicles that is augmented with visualized sensor data on both objective and subjective situation awareness (SA). In addition, the resolution of the video stream was varied. It was found that video resolution had a significant effect on objective SA. When looking at level 1 of objective SA, there was an additional interaction effect of resolution and augmentation. No significant effect of condition was found either on the other levels of objective SA or on subjective SA. In the following paragraphs, two interesting findings will be highlighted.

First, the effect on SA level 1 is in line with the hypothesis that an added value of the augmentation is to be expected for this level of SA since it pertains to the perception of relevant elements in the situation. The color-coded highlighting of other road users proved to facilitate SA in conjunction with the video resolution by increasing the road users' salience in the traffic situation. Thus, these results point into the direction of a compensatory effect of augmentation: Particularly when the video resolution is degraded, the use of sensor data augmentation has a beneficial effect on the perception level of SA. However, as no influence of augmentation on SA levels 2 and 3 was found, the enhanced perception did not affect integration and projection levels of SA.

Second, a discrepancy between effects on objective and subjective SA became evident. Neither augmentation nor resolution had a significance effect on subjective SA. This finding is interesting as it shows that even though perception was objectively improved (SA level 1), this effect did not spill over to the reported *subjective* SA. This result is in line with Endsley's [15, 16] finding that subjective SA indicators, such as SART, and objective SA indicators, such as SAGAT, measure distinct psychological constructs: While subjective SA measures were found to be correlated with confidence, they were not correlated with objective SA measures. Conclusively, objective SA measures, though self-reported, may not be immediately articulatable by participants but may rather need to be collected in a systematic, query-based approach. Our findings on objective SA also resonate with Georg et al.'s [9] outcomes in their remote driving study, underlining that video stream quality is both relevant for remote driving and remote assistance. Beyond this methodological perspective, the discrepancy between objective and subjective SA may also bear practical implications for safety. As being aware of what is happening in the traffic situation is a necessary prerequisite for assessing the situation correctly, ensuring safety, the objective improvement of SA may be desirable even when it is not reflected in a similar subjective impression.

The study comes with some limitations. First, the statistical analyses showed a high degree of dispersion. This may be due to the use of real-world video streams and visualization algorithms with limited accuracy, as is nevertheless the state of the art in object identification and classification algorithms. The lack of accuracy and resulting ambiguous visualizations might have led to confusion in identifying relevant road users in the augmented conditions. Thus, an added value of augmentation became evident only in the low-resolution conditions. Second, the video resolution was still relatively good even in the low-resolution condition. Objects could still be identified by participants in most cases. This ceiling effect might conceal a more pronounced effect of the

augmentation on SA. Third, as participants were not asked to give advice to the HAV, a lack of involvement is possible which might mask effects. In future research, the resolution of the video stream could be degraded even more to discover potential positive effects of visualized sensor data. This may increase ecological validity further as a lower resolution is a common issue in real-world data transmission. Additionally, the effect of increased accuracy of the mentioned algorithms could be investigated, reflecting technological progress.

Overall, the data gives indications for further pursuing and investigating HMIs for remote assistance that are augmented by additional sensor data. Future research could refine this framework by including features to aid attentional guidance. By increasing the salience of objects that are crucial for a traffic situation, safety and performance of HAV remote assistance could be further enhanced.

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